

Office Management System

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Abstract. The Office Management System supports internal process management in both public and private sectors. It digitizes workflows such as document submission, approval, tracking, and record keeping. There are two user roles: Admin and Employee. Employees can view their profile, request leave and employee housing, report attendance, check salary, and receive approval notifications. Admins can manage employee data, approve or reject requests, handle attendance and salary calculation, upload information, email communication, and generate reports. The system aims to improve efficiency, accuracy, and transparency within the Ministry of Planning and Finance (MOPF). It also supports collaboration between departments and simplifies document handling. The system is built using PHP, Laravel, and MySQL.

Keywords: attendance, email communication, employee housing, salary calculation.

INTRODUCTION

The Office Management System of the Ministry of Planning and Finance (MOPF) in Hinthada is an integrated digital platform designed to improve and modernize personnel management within the ministry. Prioritizing efficiency, transparency, and accuracy, the system automates essential human resource operations such as maintaining employee records, processing leave applications, managing data entry, and handling housing requests. Specifically customized for the operational context of MOPF Hinthada, the workflow management system simplifies complex HR tasks, enhances office administration, and contributes to greater productivity across the organization.

PROBLEM

The existing Office Management System has notable limitations. It is not optimized for mobile devices, which reduces usability for employees and administrators, especially in areas with poor internet connectivity.

APPROACH

The Office Management System consists of two main components, Employee and Admin. On the admin side, admin can log in to the Dashboard with their email and password. Admin can view own profile and can also manage employee profile, add new employees, upload information, manage for employee request leave and employee housing. Admin can manage salary for employees and can check employee attendance. Admin can forward emails sent by relevant departments and annual reports can be managed.

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On the employee side, employees must first have an account and log in to access the system. After logging in, they can access the employee dashboard and employees can view information uploaded by the admin and update profile image. When they want to take a leave due to personal reasons, they can fill in the leave type and leave request fields and request leave. In addition, employees can apply for employee housings and view the approval or rejection from the admin for leave requests and housing applications. Employees can sign their daily attendance lists and view their monthly payroll.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

Figure 2: Database Design

An Entity Relationship Diagram uses data modeling techniques that can help define business processes and serve as the foundation for a relational database. ER diagram of Office Management System contains nine tables. They are employee_housings table, positions table, pay_salaries table, attendances table, users table, news table, send_mails table, leave_types table and leave_requests table. The users table has one to one relationship with employee_housings table, positions table and one to many relationships with pay_salaries table, attendances table, send_mails table, leave_requests table and news table. The leave_types table is connected to leave_requests table one to many relationships.

RESULTS

Implementing an office management system offers numerous benefits to organizations. The entire leave request, profile editing and approval process, significantly improves operational efficiency by reducing the time and effort required to manually handle leave requests. The Office Management System reduces human error, ensures compliance with leave policies, and provides both employees and admins with updates on leave balances that help them make informed decisions. In addition, the system provides transparency and fairness as employees can track the status of their leave requests and view their leave history. Notifications and alerts ensure timely responses to leave requests, improving overall communication and

workflow. Management of employee record, administrative functions such as leave type configuration and role-based access control are also supported. Overall, the Office Management System is a more structured, efficient, and user-friendly system that will benefit the entire organization.

Figure 3: Displaying Three Categories for Planning Report

Figure 3 shows that the admin has divided the projects to be implemented into three categories: short-term, medium-term, and long-term, and has prepared a system that allows you to view the completion status in three categories: ongoing, completed, and overdue.

Figure 4: Planning Report for Relevant Departments

Figure 4 shows that the administrator presents a bar chart showing the budget allocated by the state to each relevant department and the projects developed by each relevant department.

CONCLUSION

The Office Management System is being implemented to manage the employees of the Ministry of Planning and Finance in Hinthada. The Office Management system plays a vital role in the effective management of human resources within the organization and enables smooth communication between employees and admin. The system is designed to streamline key administrative tasks such as leave management, employee housing requests, employee record keeping and information management, thus supporting better workforce management. Overall, the office management system is essential to optimize the internal operations of MOPF, Hinthada and enhances employees' satisfaction and organizational productivity.

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